
Supplementary Material for

**Inverse Design of FBG-based Optical Filters
Using Deep Learning: A Hybrid CNN-MLP
Approach**

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Supplement Note 1. Electromagnetic theory

The Transfer Matrix Method (TMM) is utilized in this model to solve coupled mode equations, while coupled structures are handled by married mode theory. The following is how a Fiber Bragg Grating (FBG) will effectively reflect light under the Bragg condition [1]:

$$\lambda_B = 2n_{\text{eff}}\Lambda \quad (\text{S1})$$

Where λ_B is the Bragg wavelength representation. The letters Λ and n_{eff} represent the grating period and the effective refractive index, respectively.

The distribution of refractive index, as shown in Fig. 1 and 2 (in the [main manuscript](#)). The function of $n(z)$ can be represented as follows [2]:

$$n(z) = n_0 + \Delta n_{\text{dc}}(z) + A(z)\Delta n_{\text{ac}}(z)\cos((2\pi/\Lambda)z + \theta(z)) \quad (\text{S2})$$

The symbol n_0 represents the fiber core's average change in refractive index. $A(z)$ is the representation of the apodization function. Δn_{ac} represents the highest index variation. The symbol Δn_{dc} indicates the average change in refractive index. θ represents the period chirp. Applying the coupled mode theory, one can compute a grating's reflectivity as follows [3, 4]:

$$R(L, \lambda) = \frac{\kappa^2 \sinh^2(sL)}{\Delta\beta^2 \sinh^2(sL) + s^2 \cosh^2(sL)} \quad (\text{S3})$$

$R(L, \lambda)$ denotes the reflectivity, and L represents the grating length. The coupling constant is denoted by κ , while $\Delta\beta$ refers to the detuning wave vector and s equal to $(\kappa^2 - \Delta\beta^2)^{1/2}$. The grating period in a chirped FBG changes along its length. The chirp coefficient is used as follows to vary the period:

$$\text{period} - \frac{\alpha}{2} < \Lambda(z) < \text{period} + \frac{\alpha}{2} \quad (\text{S4})$$

Where α is the chirp coefficient, z varies between 0 and L . In this work, the following apodization functions are used to design and simulate an FBG as follows [4]:

1- Uniform

$$A(z) = 1 \quad -\frac{L}{2} \leq z \leq \frac{L}{2} \quad (\text{S5})$$

2- Cosine

$$A(z) = \cos\left(\frac{\pi z}{L}\right) \quad -\frac{L}{2} \leq z \leq \frac{L}{2} \quad (\text{S6})$$

3- Raised-Cosine

$$A(z) = \cos^2\left(\frac{\pi z}{L}\right) \quad -\frac{L}{2} \leq z \leq \frac{L}{2} \quad (\text{S7})$$

4- Tanh

$$A(z) = \frac{\tanh\left[\eta\left(1 - 2\left(\frac{z}{L}\right)\right)\right]}{\tanh(\eta)} \quad -\frac{L}{2} \leq z \leq \frac{L}{2} \quad (\text{S8})$$

The parameter η can be utilized to adjust the sharpness of the apodization profile.

Supplement Note 2: FDTD simulation of FBG

The parameters selected for the simulation, outlined in Table S1, were chosen based on the specific model requirements and practical considerations crucial for FBG design. The proposed configurations' linear and nonlinear optical properties were analyzed using the Finite-Difference Time-Domain (FDTD) numerical method. By carefully selecting mesh dimensions

of 0.4 nm, we ensured the method accurately represented the system's visual response while improving spatial resolution. To minimize reflections at the borders of the simulation domain, we employed a Perfectly Matched Layer (PML) as an absorptive boundary condition. The PML has been shown to be highly effective in absorbing outgoing waves and significantly reducing reflections, thereby enhancing the accuracy of our findings.

Table S1. The Parameters Used in the Simulation

Parameter	Quantity
Free space wavelength, (nm)	1550
Period, (μm)	0.5
Modulation depth	0.0003
Cladding index	1.45
Fiber diameter, (μm)	5.25

This in-depth analysis provided valuable insights into the unique characteristics and performance of the FBG across various situations.

Supplement Note 3: DNN formulation

Having comprehensively comprehended the FBG structure depicted in Fig. 2 (in the [main manuscript](#)), we can now explore the mathematical framework underlying the forward and inverse models. These models are crucial in structuring the problem for the Deep Neural Network (DNN), creating a nexus between the input variables and the transmission spectra.

A forward model can be established by leveraging the geometric design parameters, denoted as x_i , associated with the FBG. This model enables the computation of the transmission spectrum. To ascertain the transmission spectra, y_j , the mapping function $\mathbf{M}$, and pertinent input variables can be utilized.

$$y_j = \mathbf{M}(x_1 = L, x_2 = \Lambda, x_3 = a, x_4 = \Delta n_{dc}, x_5 = \Delta n_{ac}) \quad (\text{S9})$$

Where L is grating lengths, Λ is the grating period, a is the chirp period, Δn_{dc} is variations in the average refractive index of the fiber core, and Δn_{ac} is maximum index variations. To establish the optimal estimator, we define an objective function to determine the best estimator for the forward model as follows:

$$\min_{i=1,2,\dots,6} \left\{ \left\| \hat{\mathbf{M}}(x_i) - \mathbf{g} \right\| \right\} \quad (\text{S10})$$

In the equation above, the predicted function is represented by $\hat{\mathbf{M}}$ and is compared to the ground truth, denoted as $\mathbf{g}$, which represents the actual observed values. A primary challenge in Deep Learning (DL) is identifying the optimal estimator for $\hat{\mathbf{M}}$ based on the available training data. In contrast, an inverse problem aims to reconstruct the design space from the existing transmission values. Our methodology differentiates itself from traditional approaches by using Eq. (S9) to derive a design space from the transmission spectra, where y_j represents the transmission spectra. This design space can be obtained via the following inverse function.

$$x_i = \mathbf{M}^{-1}(T_j) \quad (\text{S11})$$

Our research methodology distinguishes itself by addressing a common challenge in our field: traditional analytical methods often fall short in defining the inverse function for Fiber Bragg Grating (FBG) configurations. To overcome this obstacle, our study introduces a novel perspective by proposing the adoption of Deep Learning (DL) strategies as an alternative solution. DL excels as a powerful tool for nonlinear approximation, and our investigation advances an improved methodology for both forward and inverse models. This innovative approach provides a comprehensive understanding of FBG's complex behavior, representing a significant advancement in the discipline.

Supplement Note 4: Training Dataset Overview

This section provides a detailed overview of the training dataset utilized to train the DNN under consideration. The training dataset enables the DNN to identify hidden patterns and generate accurate predictions. With access to a complete and precise training dataset, the DNN demonstrates its ability to handle varying inputs and assign appropriate weight via the activation function of each neuron.

Dataset Specifics

Figure S1 shows the input training dataset used to train the established DNN to give a clearer idea of the dataset. The dataset comprises a substantial 1.35×10^4 samples, computed via the FDTD method, widely used in computational electromagnetics to solve Maxwell's equations numerically.

Data Curation and Quality

We carefully curated the dataset to ensure its accuracy and accuracy. It underwent rigorous testing and cleaning to eliminate noise, errors, and inconsistencies. The dataset includes a diverse range of inputs, allowing the DNN to be trained to handle each input type with precision and accuracy.

Importance of the Training Dataset

In conclusion, the training dataset was a vital component that ensured the DNN's effectiveness in identifying hidden patterns and generating accurate predictions. The carefully curated dataset, with its diverse range of inputs, enabled the DNN to be trained to handle each input type with high precision and accuracy.

Fig. S1. The histograms of the data distribution. Histograms visually represent the distribution of input and output variables. The input data set used for DNN training consists of several configurational parameters of the resonator structure, including x_1 , grating lengths; x_2 , the grating period; x_3 , the chirp period; x_4 , variations in the average refractive index of the fiber core; x_5 , maximum index variations. A histogram displays the dispersion and occurrence rates of these input factors. The uniformity across the features suggests that the input data for the NN is well-balanced, which is essential for practical model training.

Supplement Note 5: Analysis of the computational cost

In this study, we aim to examine the computational costs associated with DL techniques compared to traditional numerical methods like the Finite Element Method (FEM) and the FDTD method. Figure S2 provides a detailed breakdown of the computational expenses, measured in seconds, incurred by the FEM and FDTD methods across various meshing strategies. The purpose of this analysis is to evaluate the computational burden of the DL paradigm in comparison to FEM and FDTD techniques.

Specifically, Fig. S2 illustrates the CPU time, in seconds, required to execute the FEM and FDTD methodologies under different mesh configurations. The use of the most refined mesh size necessitated computational durations of 5907 seconds for FEM and 4612 seconds for FDTD, respectively.

Fig. S2. A comparative analysis was conducted to clarify the computational costs incurred by the FEM and the FDTD method. When utilizing the most refined mesh settings, the simulations required 5907 seconds for FEM and 4612 seconds for FDTD to complete. In contrast, employing DL methodologies significantly reduced computational time to less than a second. This substantial reduction in the duration of simulations provides a significant advantage, resulting in considerable time savings. This efficiency gain highlights the effectiveness of DL techniques in streamlining the computational process, offering a compelling alternative to traditional numerical simulation methods.

For the FDTD method, the computational time increased progressively to 4, 8, 20, 52, 123, 309, 338, 972, and 2561 seconds for mesh levels classified from extremely coarse to extra fine, respectively. Similarly, for the FEM approach, computational times escalated to 7, 14, 28, 79, 183, 438, 1310, and 3212 seconds across the same mesh gradations.

In stark contrast, implementing the DL methodology reduced the computational time to a mere fraction of a second, heralding a significant reduction in time consumption and offering substantial efficiency gains for practitioners. Our research introduces an innovative strategy whereby a DNN is trained to approximate spectral data, thereby markedly diminishing the processing time associated with the DL technique.

By amalgamating the temporal metrics of these individual components, the cumulative time required for task completion can be precisely determined. Consequently, this approach affords the capability to ascertain execution times for batches or extended epochs, thereby enabling the identification of optimal techniques and models for various complex photonic devices.

This comparative analysis highlights the considerable computational efficiency of the DL method, especially when compared with the FEM and FDTD methodologies across a range of mesh densities. The substantial reduction in processing time engendered by the DL approach paves the way for enhanced and more expeditious analysis of photonic devices, thereby fostering heightened productivity and innovation within the field.

References

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